

**IMPROVING THE TEACHING PROCESS OF IT AND
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE
APPROACH**

Murodov Oybek To'raqulovich

"ASIAN INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY"

Assistant teacher of "General technical sciences" department

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida "Informatika va axborot texnologiyalari"ni o'qitishda innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish bo'yicha metodik ishlanmalar ishlab chiqish haqida so'zlab o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot texnologiyalari, tarbiya, taqdimot, multimedia, videolavha

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье говорится о разработке методических разработок по использованию инновационных образовательных технологий при преподавании «Информатики и информационных технологий» в общеобразовательных школах.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии, образование, презентация, мультимедиа, видео.

ABSTRACT

The article talks about the development of methodological developments for the use of innovative educational technologies in the teaching of "Informatics and information technologies" in general secondary schools.

Keywords: information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process is based on certain laws and principles. Principle is derived from the Latin word "princepium", which means "basic", "initial state", "guiding idea", "generalized demand". Pedagogical technology principles are general standards and requirements to be followed in order to achieve high results in the implementation of the planned educational process. When determining them, the following circumstances are taken into account:

1. The goal of education that meets the requirements of the existing society;
2. Objective laws of the didactic process;

3. Conditions that implement the educational process;

MAIN PART

Today, when the process of renewal based on science and technology is in full swing in all aspects of the socio-economic life of our country, it is important to educate the scientific and creative activity of the young generation, including students. Scientific and creative activity, on the other hand, is an important quality characteristic of a mature person, which is based on independent and free thinking. It is clear from this that every person cannot show scientific and creative activity without having the ability to think independently. At this point, it is appropriate to mention the opinion of our head of state, "The most terrible thing is the addiction of thought, the slavery of thought."

Therefore, the formation of an independent, free creative thinker, conscious and active participant in social life, is defined as a priority of the "National Personnel Training Program".

In fact, only people who can think independently and creatively can ensure the future development of our society. After all, such people have a wide worldview and spiritual world, they quickly appreciate every change and news happening in reality, have a conscious attitude and try to justify the solution of existing problems theoretically and practically. Therefore, independent and creative thinking is the basis of scientific and creative activity of a person.

It is known that the current period is characterized by the large volume of information and the acceleration of the flow of new information. Of course, every student should be able to enjoy the available information, draw correct, logical conclusions by processing and mastering it, and be able to use it effectively in their educational and practical activities. must Therefore, in educational institutions, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of directing students to the activities of scientific and creative research.

In this regard, the decision PQ-4851 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the education system in the field of information technologies, develop scientific research and integrate them with the IT industry", along with the implementation of these tasks The ROAD MAP "on improving the quality of continuous education in the field of informatics and information technologies in 2020-2023" was approved. It aims to improve the quality of teaching informatics and information technologies in general educational institutions, to improve the quality of education in the field of informatics and information and communication technologies in higher and secondary special educational institutions, and to train young people in the fields of informatics and

information and communication technologies. implementation of measures to attract and encourage scientists to research was determined.

The development of innovative pedagogical technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, require each pedagogue-teacher to develop his professional training and pedagogical skills.

Among the issues in the focus of attention of our President and our government is the issue of informatization of the educational process, and a number of laws and decisions have been adopted to solve this issue. The basis of these laws and decisions is the widespread introduction of new information and communication and pedagogical technologies, electronic textbooks and multimedia tools into the educational process, the training of highly qualified specialists with information culture who are familiar with modern information and communication technologies and use them effectively in their professional activities. constitutes

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, in order to continue the work we have started in the field of further development of science in our country, to educate our youth as possessors of deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, and to raise it to a new, modern level, the year 2023 in our country has been designated as "Human They proposed to call it the year of "attention and quality education".

The President stated that improving the quality of education is the only correct way of development of New Uzbekistan: "As our grandfather Yusuf Khos Khajib said, "There is greatness where there is intelligence, there is greatness where there is knowledge. ladi". Therefore, it is necessary to continue the reforms we have started in this field, go to educational institutions, communicate more with teachers and trainers, and jointly solve the issues raised by them in terms of quality improvement."

Introduction of innovative technologies in the process of formation of methodical preparation of pedagogical personnel for innovative pedagogical activity prepares the ground for increasing the effectiveness of this process.

The use of innovative methods to increase the effectiveness of computer lessons, the use of innovative technologies in the educational process, has the following didactic goals:

- directing the educational process to the individual, increasing the efficiency of his acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications defined by the State Education Standard;

- to increase the professional and pedagogical training and methodical training of pedagogical personnel, to prepare them for innovative pedagogical activities;

- to increase the efficiency of lessons in the teaching of informatics and information technologies, to use innovative educational technologies, to ensure active participation in trainings based on innovative technologies, and to create a foundation for acquiring the necessary methodological knowledge, skills and qualifications for the use of innovative technologies.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of the above-mentioned didactic goals is aimed at professional training of future informatics teachers, improvement of their methodical preparation, improvement of the effectiveness of lessons in the teaching of "Informatics and information technologies" in general secondary schools. creates the need to use innovative technologies.

This requires the use of innovative technologies in the formation of methodical training of future informatics teachers, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and setting them as a priority goal for innovative pedagogical activities.

References

1. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
2. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
3. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
4. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
5. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL

SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

6. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

7. Muradov, O. (2024, January). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 46-55).

8. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 84-93.

9. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 54-63.

10. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.

11. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 91–94).

12. Муродов, О. (2024). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПОМЕЩЕНИЯХ. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3,

13. Murodov, O. (2024). TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 3, сс. 155–160).

14. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA INFORMATIKA VA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI FANINI O'QITISH JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 4, сс. 77–81).

15. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 83–92).

16. Murodov Oybek Turakulovich. (2024). Development of an automated system for controlling temperature and humidity in production rooms. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 403–409.

17. Махмудова Нигора Хикматовна. (2024). Преподавание профильных предметов в начальной школе . *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 436–444.

18. Isomova, FATQ (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 947-949.

19. G'aniyevna, P. R. F. (2022, June). МАКТАБГА ТАЙЙОРЛОВ GURUHLARI UCHUN SAVODXONLIKKA O'RGATISH MASHG'ULOTLARIDA, A'HARF-TOVUSHINI O'RGATISH METODIKASI. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 38-41).

20. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). Tarbiya turlari va ularning shaxs kamolotiga ta'siri. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 429-435.

21. Tajiddinovna, I. F. (2024). Types of education and their impact on personality development. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 469-475.

22. Исомова, Ф. Т. (2024). Виды образования и их влияние на развитие личности. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 461-468.

23. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМДА “ILK QADAM” DASTURI. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 603-608.

24. Tajiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). FIRST STEP PROGRAM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 609-614.

25. Tajiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). THE ISSUE OF EDUCATION IN PRIMARY EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 615-620.

26. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ JARAYONIDA BOLALARNING IJTIMOIIY MOSLASHUVI. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 590-595.

27. Рузиева, М. (2023). ТАРЖИМА ПЛАТФОРМАСИ-МУТАРЖИМ ЛИСОНИЙ ТАФАККУРИНИНГ КЎЗГУСИ. Наука и технология в современном мире, 2(20), 37-39.
28. Рузиева, М. Я., & Эргашева, Т. Ш. (2022). МЕТОДЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УЧЕБНЫХ СЛОВАРЕЙ НА УРОКАХ РОДНОГО ЯЗЫКА И ЧТЕНИЯ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ. Вестник науки и образования, (2-2 (122)), 29-32.
29. Narziyeva, S. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL VIEWS ON THE CHOICE OF PROFESSION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 333-336.
30. Rustamovna, N. S. (2023). UNDERSTANDING EMPATHY: AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT OF HUMAN CONNECTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 378-382.
31. Rustamovna, N. S. (2023). DEVELOPING EMPATHY IN STUDENTS. *Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 127-131. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT O'QUV JARAYONI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING MUHIM OMILI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(8), 131-139.
32. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT O'QUV JARAYONI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING MUHIM OMILI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(8), 131-139.
33. Khalilova, S. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 28, 6-11.
34. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Bo 'lajak o'qituvchi pedagogik muloqot usullarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasining zamonaviy modellari va ularni qo 'llash metodlari. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(9), 223-234.
35. XALILOVA, S. (2021). JAHON PEDAGOGIKASIDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT VA MILLIY PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT USLUBLARIGA TRANSFORMATSIYASI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).
36. Ravshanovna, K. S. (2023). Factors Affecting the Formation of a Positive Attitude to the Learning Activity in Students. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 116-122.
37. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Globallashuv sharoitida o 'quvchilar aqliy-ruhiy qiyofasini shaklantirishda muloqot uslublarining ahamiyati. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 100-106.
38. Ravshnovna, K. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE CULTURE OF COMMUNICATION IN MODERN EDUCATION AND EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 356-361.
39. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2022). BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILAR VA O'QUVCHILAR O 'RTASIDAGI MULOQOT JARAYONI VA UNGA

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. *Лучший инноватор в области науки*, 1(1), 814-819.

40. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida pedagogik muloqot usullarining o'zlashtirish jarayoniga ta'siri va ahamiyati. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(10), 803-816.

41. Xalilova Shaxlo Ravshanovna. (2024). The teacher's views on the technologies for the development of pedagogical communication methods. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(2), 368–376.

42. Халилова, Ш. Р. (2024). Технологии разработки методов педагогического общения в образовательном процессе сделанный увеличивать технологии. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 261-268.

43. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2024). PEDAGOGLAR TOMONIDAN DARSDA VA DARSDAN TASHQARI MUHITDA QO'LLANADIGAN PEDAGOGIK MULOQOTNING USLUBLARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 126-134.

44. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT AS A SOCIAL-BIOLOGICAL PHENOMENON, AS AN OBJECT AND SUBJECT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).

45. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Teachers by before school education organization in pupils passable training in the process to the children applied pedagogical communication styles classification. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 237-243.

46. O'ktam qizi Buxoro, S. M. (2022). BOLANING NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI O 'YINLAR. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 1(1), 484-486.

47. Oktam's, S. M. (2023). Methods and Tools of Speech Development of Small Group Children in Preschool Education Organization. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 104-108.

48. O'ktam qizi Shukurova, M. (2023). Speech grow up in training using interactive methods. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 357-360.

49. O'ktam qizi Shukurova, M. (2023). The importance of genres of folklore in the education of preschool children. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 96-99.

50. Shukurova, M. (2023). METHODS AND METHODS OF INCREASING CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN A PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 477–480.

51. Madina O'ktamovna Shukurova. (2024). " Growing children's speech in the process of introducing them to the environment and nature ". *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 130–135.

52. Shukurova, M. (2024). OILADA FARZAND TARBIYASIDA OTANING ROLI. ZAMONAVIY TARAQQIYOTDA ILM-FAN VA MADANIYATNING O‘RNI, 3(2), 162-167.
53. O‘ktamovna, S. M. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA TABIAT BURCHAGINI TAYYORLASH. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 661-667.
54. O‘ktamovna, S. M. (2024). EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY GRADES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 654-660.
55. O‘ktamovna, S. M. (2024). PREPARATION OF THE NATURE CORNER IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 675-681.
56. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2023). НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОЗДАНИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СЛУЖБЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *ЛКИИСИ РАН, МАПН, 2023–267 с.*, 13.
57. Баратов, Ш. Р., & Сабирова, Д. А. (2016). Социальный интеллект как необходимое качество педагога. *История российской психологии в лицах: Дайджест-ISSN 2415-7953 (РИНЦ)*, (6).
58. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2018). Психологик хизмат: Магистрлар учун дарслик. *Т.: “Наврўз” нашриёти*, 344.
59. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2015). A role of social intellect and social competence in professional development of a teacher in the intense training system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 3(4), 43-48.
60. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2012). Социальный Интеллект: Структура и Функции. *Психология XXI столетия*, 2, 153-158.
61. Баротов, Ш. Р. (1995). Ўқувчи шахсини ўрганиш усуллари. *Т.: Ўқитувчи*, 57.
62. Баратов, Ш. Р. (2021). Из опыта внедрения концепции психологической службы в Узбекистане. “XXI АСР ПСИХОЛОГИЯСИ” МАВЗУСИДАГИ ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АНЖУМАНИ МАҚОЛАЛАР ТЎПЛАМИ, 5.
63. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2017). Психологическая служба образования: от теории к практике. (Учебно-методическое пособие). *Бухара: Дурдона*.